

THE IMPACT PROPERTIES OF METAL-COMPOSITE LAMINATES**P.J. HOGG AND A. AHMADNIA**Department of Materials,
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UK**ABSTRACT**

Laminated structures consisting of plies of dissimilar materials may be regarded as macrocomposites. Such systems have traditionally been used to exploit the physical properties of the various constituents and little attempt has been made to study their mechanical properties. In this programme a macrocomposite system consisting of thin stainless steel sheet, 0.6mm, bonded to sheet moulding compound (SMC), 2mm-6mm, was studied under impact conditions. An instrumented falling weight impact test machine was used to subject the laminates to low energy, non-penetrating impacts of speeds 1-3m/s, with energies ranging from 10-87J. Additional tests were performed on the constituent materials, SMC and steel. It was determined that the macrocomposite laminate was an efficient energy absorbing system and that the SMC layer in a thin, 2.6mm laminate, could absorb more than twice as much energy as a comparable sheet of SMC subjected to an excess energy total penetration impact, and tested in isolation.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of composites as structural materials has largely become synonymous with fibre-reinforced systems and the properties of other classes of composite have not been as widely studied. Many structural composites may be formed at the macroscopic level, e.g. in the form of laminated sheet, from materials that cannot feasibly be combined at the microscopic level. Such "macro-composite" systems inhabit the grey area between materials and structures and when examples of this class of composite are used in practice it is usually to exploit the respective physical properties of each layer, such as corrosion resistance and conductivity. Examples of plastics lining metals are common and now increasingly metals are being used to line composites (1,2). Little attention has been paid to the mechanical properties of macrocomposites, although experience with fibre composites in the form of laminated plies of varying orientation has shown that the mechanical properties of multilayer systems are not always a simple function of the properties of each layer, particularly if strength is the property in question (3).

If the exploitation of laminated macrocomposites is to continue then information regarding the mechanical behaviour of such systems under a range of conditions is required, and the link between laminate and constituent properties must be established.

This paper presents some initial results from a programme studying the mechanical properties of laminates comprised of sheet metals and both plastics and reinforced plastics. The specific properties reported here concern the impact response of composites produced from single sheets of stainless steel and sheet moulding compound (SMC) bonded together.

The test programme involved instrumented falling weight impact (IFWI) tests on both the macrocomposite laminates and the constituent sheet materials. In this paper the basic impact properties of the laminates, as measured by the IFWI test are reported. This consists primarily of the force-time and force-deflection curves together with the energy absorbed by the system. The absolute energy absorbing characteristics of the macrocomposite were also of interest and it was discovered that this combination of materials represents a very efficient energy absorbing system.

MATERIALS

The materials used in this study consisted of compression moulded SMC, stainless steel and laminates consisting of single sheets of stainless steel bonded to SMC. The SMC was supplied ready moulded in plaques 102 mm by 264mm with nominal wall thicknesses of 2, 4 and 6mm. The resin system was Scott Bader Crystic D4029 and the nominal glass content was 30% by weight.

The steel sheet was a nickel-chrome type 304 stainless steel, thickness 0.6mm. The SMC-steel laminates were prepared by directly moulding the SMC onto the steel sheet which had been primed by the application of Scott Bader primer, Crestomer 1163. By varying the charge of SMC with a constant thickness of steel, laminates 102mm by 264mm were prepared with a nominal wall thickness of 2.6, 4.6, and 6.6mm. All moulding was performed by Scott Bader Ltd. Square test specimens, 6cm by 6cm, for impact tests were cut from the moulded plaques using a fine band saw. No other specimen preparation was required.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Plate specimens were subjected to falling weight impact tests using an instrumented CEAST drop tower in conjunction with an AFS Mk 3 fracturescope. In accordance with ISO/DISS 6603/1 the specimens were supported by a 40mm diameter steel ring and centrally impacted by a hardened steel striker with a 20mm diameter hemispherical tip. The striker is instrumented by means of a strain gauge bridge mounted just behind the hemispherical tip. The raw data recorded during the impact event consists of a force-time record which is captured by a transient recorder and processed by a dedicated microcomputer. The velocity immediately prior to impact is measured by an electronic flag device. This datum enables the

microcomputer to calculate the force-deflection, velocity-time, displacement-time and energy-time curves in addition to the force-time record. No filtering of the test data is performed at any stage. The striker itself is mounted on a carriage system with an inclusive weight of approximately 19kg. The velocity of impact and the incident energy of the striker (referred to throughout as the impact energy), are simultaneously varied by adjusting the drop height. The load cell of the striker was rated to 19kN which represented a limiting factor when testing laminates incorporating a steel layer. At the time of these experiments the equipment was not fitted with an anti-rebound device. The majority of tests reported involve non-penetrating impacts and consequently each impact event was in reality a series of blows of decaying magnitude. The assumption is made that the subsequent impacts produce no additional damage over and above that caused by the initial blow. The veracity of this assumption will be determined in a later series of experiments on modified equipment. Impact testing was performed, on unclamped specimens, at room temperature (16-20°C) at a range of velocities and energies. In the case of SMC/steel laminates, the steel layer was always loaded in tension with the impactor striking the SMC surface.

In order to assess the work done in deforming the steel layer in the macrocomposite during impact, indentation tests were performed on lightly clamped sheet steel. A jig that reproduced the loading configuration during impact was moulded onto a conventional tension-compression test machine and tests performed at a cross-head speed of 5mm/min.

a

b

Figure 1. SMC, thickness 4mm, after impact at a) 2m/s, b) 1m/s.

RESULTS

SMC specimens exhibited a common failure mode, irrespective of specimen thickness, after excess energy, penetrating, impact, figure 1a. The damaged zone consisted of a central hole surrounded by hinged, triangular flaps of material. All of the damage appeared to be constrained well within the boundaries of the test support ring, indicated by the circular marking on the specimen. The SMC was severely damaged in the vicinity of the hole, exhibiting extensive fibre and resin microcracking and delamination. A specimen subjected to a lower energy, non-penetrating impact, figure 1b, illustrates the initial stages of damage development.

It was impossible to rupture the SMC-steel laminates during this initial study and a typical example of the non-penetrated specimens after impact is shown in figure 2a. The main feature of such specimens is the large dome formed in the steel sheet as a result of plastic deformation during the impact. The domed region extended as far as the test support ring and the height of the dome, h figure 2, was dependant on the impact energy. Microcracking was also evident on the SMC surface, although this appeared to be reduced in comparison to that exhibited by SMC in isolation after non-penetrating impacts, at similar energies.

a

b

Figure 2. SMC-stainless steel specimen after impact at 2m/s viewed from a) the steel surface, indicating the dome height, h and b) the SMC surface showing limited microcracking.

Typical force-time curves for both SMC and SMC-steel laminates are shown in figures 3a and 4a respectively. The diagrams each show the curves for three specimens of equal thickness subjected to a range of impact energies and therefore velocities. For each material, the duration of the impact event appeared to be constant, irrespective of impact speed, with the duration being slightly longer for the SMC specimens. It is apparent that for both classes of material the behaviour at each testing speed was equivalent up to the point of an initial peak. This peak is quite distinct in the case of the SMC-steel laminates but less obvious for the SMC itself. After this point the curves for each test speed appear different and it is important to note that this is not, in itself, an indication of any rate effects in the material. If the force-deflection curves are considered, figures 3b and 4b, then a better physical understanding of the deformation during impact may be obtained. The curves shown are all from specimens where a non-penetrating impact occurred. The initial loading stage was therefore followed by a period of unloading and partial elastic recovery with a permanent deflection after unloading observed in all cases. For the SMC-steel specimens, figure 4b, it is apparent that each specimen followed the same loading curve, subject only to inter-specimen scatter, with the effect of the varying impact speed being to alter the point at which the unloading sequence begins. The SMC results, figure 3b, exhibited a similar behaviour at first. Subsequently however, the individual curves followed different paths as the material underwent a stage where an increase in deflection was accompanied by a decrease in load. The transition point from a regime of increasing deflection with increasing load to one of increasing deflection with decreasing load varied with the impact speed and may represent a genuine rate effect.

Figure 3. a) force-time and b) force deflection curves for SMC, thickness 4mm, for impact at 1, 1.5 and 2m/s.

Figure 4. a) force-time and b) force-deflection curves for SMC-stainless steel laminates, for impact at 1, 1.5 and 2m/s.

Figure 5. Peak force versus impact energy for three different thicknesses of a) SMC and b) SMC-stainless steel.

It has been determined (4) that the initial peak force exhibited by the SMC specimens corresponded to the onset of cracking, which occurred initially at the tensile loading surface. No damage was detected in specimens sectioned and examined after loading to a lower level. The initial peak in the SMC-steel specimens corresponds to the onset of plastic deformation in the steel (4). The maximum load is often quoted as a parameter to characterise the impact strength of a material. In this case, the physical significance of the maximum force is open to question. For the SMC-steel laminates, the maximum force corresponded to the maximum deflection but for SMC, as there was a stage where the load fell while the deflection increased, the maximum load corresponded to neither the onset of cracking nor the maximum deflection.

Figure 5 shows the variation of peak force versus impact energy for the SMC (a) and SMC-steel specimens (b) for each thickness tested. The curves rise continuously for the SMC-steel where the specimens were not ruptured, but level off for the SMC after the specimens were completely ruptured.

The energy absorbed by specimens during impact was calculated from the force-deflection curves and a typical trace (for both SMC and SMC-steel) obtained from a non-penetrating impact is shown in figure 6. The energy rose steadily to a peak value that corresponded to the kinetic energy of the striker immediately prior to impact. It should be noted that the point of maximum energy absorption does not necessarily correspond to the point of maximum force (as is the case for SMC-steel), but always coincides with the maximum deflection. After this point specimens exhibit a degree of elastic recovery and the energy absorbed falls somewhat, levelling out at a value equal to the total energy absorbed by the system during the impact event.

Figure 6. Typical energy-time curve for a non-penetrating impact (in this case for a SMC-stainless steel laminate, 2.6mm thick).

The total energy absorbed by SMC specimens is shown in figure 7a as a function of the impact energy. Each thickness exhibited a linear relationship between these energy terms up until reaching a plateau corresponding to total penetration of the specimen by the impactor. The magnitude of this plateau increased with, and was proportional to, specimen thickness. The linear portion of the curve did not pass through the origin as a certain finite elastic energy had to be supplied to the material before energy could be permanently absorbed by fracture processes. This elastic energy threshold was very small compared to the total energy that could be absorbed by irreversible fracture processes and increased with specimen thickness. It is apparent from these results that increasing the impact velocity and impact energy beyond a certain level had no effect on the amount of energy absorbed by the material. The maximum energies absorbed by SMC were 16J, 52J and 82J for 2, 4 and 6mm sheet respectively.

The relationship between impact energy and absorbed energy for the SMC-steel laminates is shown in figure 7b. As these tests were not carried out over a sufficiently high range of impact energies, the ultimate energy absorbing properties could not be ascertained. The general features of these curves were however the same as those for SMC, figure 7a and SMC-steel laminates were shown to be capable of absorbing a significant quantity of energy without fracture.

Figure 7. Absorbed energy versus impact energy (incident kinetic energy of striker) for a) SMC and b) SMC-stainless steel, for three different thicknesses.

DISCUSSION

The macrocomposite absorbed energy on impact by a combination of plastic deformation in the steel and brittle microcracking in the SMC. The important question is whether or not the laminate absorbed more (or less) energy than the individual constituents would do in isolation. The answer to this question effectively determines whether one is justified in classing the macrocomposite as a material rather than a structure. It could be argued that changes in the deformation profile of the steel, leading to a change in the total volume of plastically deformed metal, or a change in the density and extent of microcracking in the SMC, could occur as a result of their combination in the macrocomposite.

The key to evaluating the behaviour of the macrocomposite was, in this case, the steel sheet. The deformation profile of the steel sheet, when subject to indentation and impact was exactly analogous to that observed in the steel when it is a component part of the macrocomposite. Force-deflection curves obtained for the steel from indentation tests and impact at 5mm/min and 4m/s respectively were identical, confirming that the properties of this f.c.c. austenitic steel are insensitive to rate. Furthermore, when a steel sheet was progressively loaded and unloaded to an increasing level, the loading stage of the curve continued to fall on the force-deflection curve for continuous monotonic loading. The work done in producing a

Figure 8. a) load-deflection curves for steel sheet used to construct calibration curve
b) linking permanent deflection with work done.

Figure 9. Energy absorbed versus impact energy for 2mm SMC, 2.6mm SMC-stainless steel, 2mm SMC' (SMC layer in the macrocomposite).

given permanent deflection in the steel sheet was obtained from the loading and unloading curves, figure 8a, by measuring the area under the curves, and a calibration curve produced, figure 8b. It was then straightforward to determine the work done in deforming the steel component of the macrocomposite during impact by simply measuring the permanent deflection (dome height) of the steel and reading the relevant value from figure 8b.

Once the energy absorbed by the steel was known, the energy absorbed by the SMC could be calculated and compared to the behaviour of SMC in isolation. This exercise was performed for the 2.6mm SMC-steel laminates, figure 9. The diagram shows the energy absorbed by the macrocomposite, the energy absorbed just by the SMC layer (designated SMC') and the energy absorbed by a comparable, 2mm thick SMC sheet tested in isolation. At a given impact energy, the SMC' initially absorbed less energy than the SMC sheet. This was because, at low energies, the elastic energy absorbed by the steel was significant. As the impact energy rose, so the energy absorbed by the SMC' became progressively larger relative to that absorbed by the SMC until, at the largest impact energy tested (80J), the SMC' absorbed almost two and a half times the maximum energy that could be absorbed by the SMC.

These findings clearly show that the macrocomposite was not behaving simply as the aggregate of its two constituent parts and that a genuine synergistic effect exists. To date this phenomenon has not been confirmed for laminates of increased thickness as testing at the necessary impact speeds would result in forces that exceeded the capacity of the load cell of the machine. Nevertheless it is expected that the presence of the steel layer would generally be to increase the energy absorbing capabilities of the SMC. The likely cause of the observed effects is that the steel, which can sustain a far greater deflection before fracture than the SMC, supports the SMC layer, to deflections beyond those at which fracture would normally occur. The SMC therefore sustains load over a greater range enabling a greater damage density to be developed and more energy to be absorbed. These concepts are currently under investigation and the detailed form of damage development in SMC, both in isolation and in the macrocomposite, is being studied.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The maximum energy absorbed by SMC during impact is a function of thickness.
- 2) The addition of a steel layer to the SMC to form a macrocomposite substantially increases the energy absorbing capacity of the laminate.
- 3) The SMC layer within the macrocomposite absorbs considerably more energy than is possible in a comparable sheet of SMC tested in isolation.

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